

Co-funded by
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A lifetime with language: the nature and ontogeny of linguistic communication (LangInLife)

Data Management Plan

VERSION 3

28 April 2026

*Data Management Plan created using Data Stewardship Wizard.
Corresponds with Horizon Europe DMP template.*

History of changes

<i>Version</i>	<i>Publication date</i>	<i>Changes</i>
<i>Version 1.0</i>	<i>02 Jul 2025</i>	-
<i>Version 1.1</i>	<i>02 Oct 2025</i>	<i>Detailed information on potential data re-use, resources allocation, and data security added to the corresponding sections.</i>
<i>Version 2.0</i>	<i>08 Jan 2026</i>	<i>Revisions reflecting the progress of the project and practical aspects of data sharing; added Zenodo community link; minor wording revisions.</i>
<i>Version 3.0</i>	<i>28 Apr 2026</i>	<i>Subchapter Published datasets added, OSF added to repositories.</i>

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Project

We will be working on the following project for which the data and work are described in this DMP.

A lifetime with language: the nature and ontogeny of linguistic communication, CZ.02.01.01/00/23_025/0008726

Acronym

LangInLife

Start date

2025-01-01

End date

2028-12-31

Funding

- https://msmt.gov.cz: CZ.02.01.01/00/23_025/0008726 (granted)

The project focuses on the language of the individual, which is an irreplaceable means of communication with the surroundings of every person. It explores how language is acquired in childhood, how it functions in adulthood and what challenges individuals face as they age. The aim of the project is to conduct interdisciplinary research based on a combination of linguistics, psychology and neuroscience, which, by producing cutting-edge results, will enable an adequate and effective response to the global language-related challenges of contemporary society.

The project has three main research objectives, carried out by research teams from participating institutes. Research objectives are referred to as R01, R02 and R03 in this DMP.

- Research objective 1: **Language in childhood: acquisition and early language development (R01)**
- Research objective 2: **Language in adulthood: nature, communication, language learning and the consequences of migration (R02)**
- Research objective 3: **Language in old age: loss of language abilities and how to slow it down (R03)**

1. Data Summary

Different types of data will be created, acquired, and re-used during the project, as detailed in this section. Data related to scientific publications will be made available, in accordance with Open Science principles and following legal requirements, as described in Section 2.

The project will generate a variety of data surrounding nature and ontogeny of linguistic communication. The generated data will be both quantitative (e.g., reaction times) and qualitative (e.g., annotated spoken and written corpora). All data will relate to research questions for each of the research objectives as outlined in the project proposal. The data will encompass different methodological approaches.

The expected size of the data differs for each of the research objectives; the expected increase in a year is hundreds of GiB for R01, under 10 GiB for R02, and 550 GiB for R03.

The data obtained will be useful not only for the project's research team, but also for the wider community of experts in the fields of linguistics, psychology, neuroscience, pedagogy, and clinical practice. The data can serve as reference material for further research into language development, bilingualism, the impact of aging on language abilities, and the impact of migration on language acquisition.

- **Equipment data**

Data will be collected by project members, with our own equipment, which is well described and known.

The following types of equipment will be used:

- Eye-tracking
- Electroencephalogram (EEG)
- Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)
- Functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS)

Data will be handled in the following formats: BVCF, CSV, EDF, FNIRS, NIFTI, and other formats depending on the used equipment and software.

- **Experimental stimuli**

We will be using audio, video and image data as stimuli in experiments.

We will be working with the following formats: DOCX, JPG, MP3, PNG, TXT, WAV, and other formats depending on the software used.

Published datasets

- **Neighborhood frequency effects in late bilingual phonological neighborhoods**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17431193>

Other researchers working in the same field might be interested in using the data.

- **Possible uses of syntactic complexity annotation in a parallel corpus: The case of French -ant forms in converbal function and their Czech counterparts**
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17912727>
Other researchers working in the same field might be interested in using the data.

Re-used data

We will be re-using the following data:

- **Openly available linguistic corpora**
(e.g. Czech national corpus, Clearpond, English Vocabulary Profile)

The corpora will be used to study linguistic phenomena related to research objectives. The data can be used in the format provided without any conversion needed. We will work with them using online analytical tools or download them for local analysis. Potential changes in the data will not influence the reproducibility of our results. For some corpora, only parts of them will be used; any filtering or selection will be documented.

- **Copyrighted text corpora**
(e.g. Brepolis database, printed books)

The corpora will be used to study linguistic phenomena related to research objectives. Texts needed for analysis are available via subscription to the database or purchase of the books (not part of the project costs). There will not be any changes in the data influencing our results. Only parts of the texts will be used, and the selection will be documented.

- **Datasets previously created by project members**

Datasets will be used to study linguistic phenomena related to research objectives. Project members are the owners of the datasets. The datasets can be used in the format provided without any conversion needed. We already have a copy of the data. Those are fixed datasets, changes will not influence the reproducibility of our results. For some, only parts of the dataset will be used; any filtering or selection will be documented.

1.1 Data formats

Information about each of data formats we currently plan to be working with.

- **BrainVision Core Data Format (BVCDF)**
 - An open proprietary format, compliant with BIDS (Brain Image Data Structure) standard.
- **Comma-separated Values (CSV)**
 - An open file format, suitable for long-term preservation of tabular data.
- **Office Open XML Document (DOCX)**
 - A widely used format, following the Office Open XML standard.
- **European Data Format (EDF)**

- An open format, suitable for exchange and storage of multichannel biological and physical signals.
- **JPEG, JPG**
 - A format suitable for long-term preservation of raster images.
- **JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)**
 - An open file and data interchange format.
- **Markdown (MD)**
 - An open file format.
- **MP3**
 - An open audio file format.
- **Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative (NIfTI)**
 - An open file format, used to store brain imaging data obtained using MRI methods.
- **Portable Network Graphics (PNG)**
 - A format suitable for long-term preservation of raster images.
- **R (R)**
 - A format for programming files used in open-source software for statistical computing and graphics, R.
- **R Markdown (RMD)**
 - Format of files used in open-source software for statistical computing and graphics, R, using Markdown markup language.
- **Share Near InfraRed File (SNIRF)**
 - An open file format, with specifications compliant with BIDS (Brain Image Data Structure) standard.
- **Text File (TXT)**
 - A format suitable for long-term preservation of textual data.
- **Waveform Audio Format (WAV)**
 - A proprietary audio file format.
- **Office Open XML Workbook (XLSX)**
 - A widely used format, following the Office Open XML standard.

2. FAIR Data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

We will share data that can become open in publicly accessible trusted repositories using descriptive metadata as required by the repository. Keywords will be added for better findability.

Metadata will be available in a form that can be harvested and indexed. All published data will be assigned a persistent identifier which will be included in their metadata. This will be managed by the repositories.

The following metadata standards are relevant for various data we will work with during the project:

- **Brain Imaging Data Structure** (BIDS)
- **Component Metadata Specification** (CMDI)
- **Investigation Description Format** (IDF)
- **Linguistic Annotation Format** (LAF)
- **Minimum Information about an fMRI Study** (MIfMRI)
- **Open Language Archives Community Metadata** (OLAC Metadata)

2.2. Making data accessible

We will be working with philosophy *as open as possible* for our data. Data will be deposited by the publication date of the related scientific publication at the latest; embargo period is currently not planned to be used for any of the datasets.

The following repositories have already been used for storing the data:

- **Zenodo**
 - A trusted general open repository, operated by CERN; now with a curated project community: zenodo.org/communities/langinlife
- **OSF Data Archive**
 - Service provided by OSF; repository for preserving datasets from OSF projects, upon request.

The following repositories are considered for storing the data:

- **Figshare**
 - A trusted general repository, operated by Digital Science company.
- **Dataverse**
 - A trusted general repository, operated by Harvard.

Other trusted general or disciplinary repositories might be specified as further updates to this DMP.

Our data cannot become completely open. We will collect data connected to a person, i.e. personal data, as detailed in Section 6. We can use pseudonymization, anonymization and data aggregation to make the data more openly available.

There are IP reasons why our data cannot be open, which applies to re-used copyrighted text corpora.

For data with limited access, there will be clear instructions on how to get access in the metadata.

Metadata will be made openly available. This will be managed by the repositories.

2.3. Making data interoperable

We will be sharing data in the following formats:

- CSV, JSON, TXT, PDF

More formats will be decided upon closer to the publication date and will be specified as updates to this DMP. For sharing data, we will use open formats as opposed to proprietary ones whenever possible.

2.4. Increase data re-use

Rich metadata and documentation will be provided for each dataset. Files and folders will be versioned and structured using a file naming convention.

For experiments, we will use paper and electronic lab notebooks to make sure that there is good provenance of the data analysis. The following open-source research software will be used for experiments:

- **PCibex**, an open-source software for internet-based experiments
- **L-Rex**, an open-source software for linguistic experiments
- **PsychoPY**, an open-source behavioral research software

It is clear who owns data and documents created during the project and can license them for re-use.

We will be employing the following quality processes for instrument data:

- Calibrating measurements
- Repeat measurements
- Standardized data capture and recording
- Data Entry validation

To validate the integrity of the results, the following will be done:

- We will run a subset of our jobs several times across the different computing infrastructures.

- We will be instrumenting the tools into pipelines and workflows using automated tools.
- We will use independently developed duplicate tools or workflows for critical steps to reduce or eliminate human errors.
- We will run part of the data set repeatedly to catch unexpected changes in results.

For the datasets that we re-use, conditions are as follows:

- **Openly available linguistic corpora:** The corpora are freely available with an obligation to quote the source.
- **Copyrighted text corpora:** Texts are available under specific restrictions which we will follow in our project. Material is subject to copyright and, in some cases, located in the publisher's owned databases; its use is permitted for research purposes only. Data will be cited and referred to in an appropriate format.
- **Datasets previously created by project members:** Project members are rightsholders for those datasets. The datasets are freely available with an obligation to quote the source if the dataset was previously published.

3. Other research outputs

Following established practices in participating research teams, **Open Science Framework (OSF)** platform will be used for preregistration of research and sharing of research data, supporting transparency of the whole research process.

Other research outputs (protocols, models, workflows) will in relevant cases be shared as part of the published data.

4. Allocation of resources

FAIR is a central part of our data management; it is considered at every decision in our data management plan. We use the FAIR principles ourselves to make our use of the data as efficient as possible.

We will be archiving data for long-term preservation after the project but also already during the project. Long-term data archiving is ensured by institutional infrastructure. Data from RO1 will be stored at the Czech Academy of Sciences for a minimum of 3 years, while data from RO2 and RO3 will be stored at Masaryk University for at least 5 years. These costs are covered by institutional budgets and do not require additional project funding. The decision whether to extend the renewal will be based on the available institutional budget as well as both the actual and predicted use of the archived data.

The time and effort required for data preparation, documentation, and publication are included in the personnel costs of the project. Researchers, in cooperation with the data steward, will dedicate part of their work hours to data curation and metadata creation. The specific hours and costs depend on the complexity of the datasets.

The repositories currently considered do not charge fees for data deposition. Should any repository require payment in the future, the project team will evaluate the cost-effectiveness.

No additional hardware or software is required beyond what is already available at the participating institutions.

Pavel Caha, Lubomíra Nováková, Radek Šimík, and Filip Smolík are responsible for finding, gathering, and collecting data for each of the research objectives, and for reviewing, enhancing, cleaning, or standardizing metadata and the associated data submitted for storage, use and maintenance within a data center or repository.

Pavla Martinková is responsible for the management and proficiency of data policies, data guidelines, and data availability.

To execute this DMP, we do not require any hardware or software in addition to what is available at the institutes.

5. Data security

The following types of data storage will be used during the project: portable media, local storage, local network and cloud storage, external storage with institutional contract (e.g., CESNET OwnCloud, OneDrive). All data centres where project data is stored carry sufficient security measures.

We are running the project in collaboration between different groups and institutes. The data are handled separately, using the infrastructure of the participating institutes. Each participating institution follows its own internal data management policies, which include regular backups and access control procedures.

Storage and backup procedures

- Data will be stored on secure institutional servers with daily automated backups.
- Sensitive data (e.g., MRI scans) will be stored on dedicated infrastructure with restricted access and encrypted storage.
- Portable media and external storage will be encrypted.

Access and security

- Access to data will be controlled via institutional authentication systems.
- Only authorized project members will have access to sensitive datasets.
- Pseudonymization keys will be stored separately and accessible only to designated personnel.

Risk management

- Project members have received training on data protection and cybersecurity risks.
- Anonymization and pseudonymization will be applied as early as possible in the data lifecycle to minimize risks related to personal data.

The risk of information loss, information leak, and information vandalism in the project or organization is acceptably low. All project web services use secure HTTPS protocols.

6. Ethics

We will collect data connected to a person, i.e. personal data. We explored General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) considerations and relevant materials. We ask the data subjects for their consent. Relevant research ethics documents and established laboratory practices will be followed.

The data subjects will be informed as follows: consent forms and participant information sheets will be used. The procedure for obtaining consent from data subjects is set as follows: Each participant will be informed about the data collected, the interest of the study, and the potential risks. The purpose of processing personal data can be described as follows: Research purposes.

The data collection is subject to ethical legislation and is covered by ethical review. It involves human subjects (RO1 and RO3), including children (RO1). Institutional research ethics committees of partner institutions have reviewed or will review any experiments concerning human subjects, as part of the established research practices of the institutes.

7. Other issues

We used the [Data Stewardship Wizard](#) with its *Common DSW Knowledge Model* (ID: dsw:root:2.6.10) knowledge model as a base for this DMP. More specifically, we used the <https://dsw.muni.cz:443/wizard> DSW instance. Updates are made in MS Word.

We will be using the following policies and procedures for data management:

- **Charles University Research Data Policy**
<https://cuni.cz/UKEN-1958.html>
This policy applies to all researchers from Charles university (CU) and any affiliated persons conducting or supporting research at CU. Data collection, storage, preservation and sharing procedures are described, in accordance with FAIR principles.
- **Research Data Policy, Measure of the Director of CEITEC MU No. 4/2020**
https://is.muni.cz/do/ceitec/uredni_deska/opatreni_reditele/opatreni_reditele_2020_04_-_research_data_policy/107763757/Directors_Measure_2020-04_Research_Data_Policy_EN.pdf
This policy applies to all research activities conducted at CEITEC MU and to data resulting from the usage of CEITEC MU core facilities, therefore it applies to RO3 of this project. Data management and storage procedures are specified and will be followed for the respective data.
- **Core Facility Data Management, CEITEC MU**
https://mafil.ceitec.cz/en/research-data-handling/#data_management
These procedures apply to data resulting from the usage of CEITEC MU core facilities, therefore it applies to RO3 of this project. Specific data storage procedures are described, including destruction of old data and data security.